

Kinetics and mechanism of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (tetralin) by Ce^{IV} in aqueous nitric acid medium

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Abstract : The kinetics and mechanism of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (tetralin) by Ce^{IV} in aqueous nitric acid to tetralone under the conditions [TL] >> [Ce^{IV}] at different temperatures (30–50 °C) have been studied in 3.0 mol dm⁻³ nitric acid medium. The experimentally observed rate law conforms to

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = kK[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{TL}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]/1 + K[\text{TL}] + K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$$

Keywords : Tetralin, Ru^{III}, kinetics, Ce^{IV}, oxidation, mechanism.

Introduction

Different oxygenated derivatives of tetralin are of much interest to the pharmaceutical industries as precursors for the production of hormone – analogs, sedatives and tranquilizers. Recently we have reported Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of α -picolines (which resemble alkyl benzene) by ceric ammonium nitrate in acid medium¹. This process has many advantages such as minimization of chemical wastage and moderation of reaction times as compared to uncatalysed paths. Hence, an attempt has been made to report a simple chemo selective method for partial oxidation of aliphatic cyclic system present in tetralin.

Results and discussion

Under the conditions at [HNO₃] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹, [Ru^{III}] = 7.25 × 10⁻⁵ and [TL] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, the rate of disappearance of Ce^{IV} shows a first order dependence on [Ce^{IV}] up to 70–85%. The observed pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) are independent of the initial concentrations of Ce^{IV} in 2.0 to 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ range.

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \text{ or } -d \ln [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k_1$$

At a fixed [Ce^{IV}] and [Ru^{III}], the order in [TL] is found to be fractional as estimated from the slopes of linear plot ($r = 0.9888$) of log k_1 vs [TL] over the concentration range of 1.0 × 10⁻² to 10 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³. These

reactions were studied at [HNO₃] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ and [Ce^{IV}] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

Oxidation of the title substrate by Ce^{IV} in aqueous nitric acid medium was found to be kinetically sluggish. In the presence of Ru^{III} the process becomes fairly fast and the rates are quite measurable. Hence it is worthwhile to take up the title investigation. It is well established from our studies that [Ru(H₂O)₅Cl]²⁺ is a reactive species in acidic medium². The fractional order observed in [Ru^{III}] was evaluated from the slope of the linear plot of log k_1 versus log [Ru^{III}]. The fractional order dependence of rate on [TL] as well as [Ru^{III}] indicate involvement of TL in complex formation with Ru^{III}. This complex is assumed to react with Ce^{IV} in the rate determining step to form a Ru^{IV}-complex. The Ru^{IV}-complex being unstable decomposes to Ru^{III} in a first order reaction step. Further, oxidations in sequence of one electron steps yield the product, tetralone. At constant ionic strength the rate of oxidation is linearly dependent on [H⁺], indicating that [Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂] is the reactive species in the oxidation³.

On addition of acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture a white precipitate of polyacrylonitrile was obtained, indicating the formation of free radical of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene. Based on experimental data and occurrence of

polymerization, the most probable mechanism could be written as :

and Scheme 1 leads to

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{TL}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{1 + K[\text{TL}] + K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (1)$$

or

$$\frac{-2.3 d \log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_1 = \frac{kK[\text{TL}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{1 + K[\text{TL}] + K[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (2)$$

Scheme 1

where k_1 is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant, k is the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step and K is the formation constant of the Ru^{III} -complex. Eq. (1) accounts for the first order dependence in Ce^{IV} and fractional order dependence in $[\text{TL}]$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ as observed experimentally. Taking reciprocal of eq. (2) we get,

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{1}{[\text{TL}]} \left[\frac{1}{kK[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} + \frac{1}{k} \right] + \frac{1}{k[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (3)$$

A plot of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[\text{TL}]$ is linear, the slope of which is equal to $1/kK$. The ratio of intercept to the slope gives the value of K and the reciprocal of intercept gives the values of k and these values are tabulated in Table 1.

The reactions were studied at different temperatures. The rates of reaction is increased with increase in temperature. From the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_1$ versus $1/T$ (Table 1), thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of tetralin were evaluated. The more negative ΔS^\ddagger ($-173 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) value indicates formation of more ordered transition state possible during the oxidation of tetralin.

Table 1. Dependence of the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) on $[\text{TL}]$ and temperature

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 3.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 5.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 7.25 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$10^2 [\text{Tetralin}]$	Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$10^4 k_1$	$6 + \log k_1$
10	30	2.50	2.39
20	-	3.63	2.55
40	-	4.57	2.66
50	-	5.37	2.72
100	-	6.90	2.83
10	30	2.50	2.39
-	35	3.45	2.57
-	40	4.22	2.62
-	45	4.79	2.68
-	50	7.00	2.84

Activation parameters :

E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	47.8 (± 0.25)
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	45.2 (± 0.25)
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	98 (± 0.25)
ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	-173 (± 0.25)

Stoichiometry :

Under experimental conditions stoichiometry of Ce^{IV} - TL redox reaction was determined. Excess concentration of TL over that of Ce^{IV} solution was allowed to react in the presence of Ru^{III} catalyst for 24 h and the completion of the reaction was ensured by TLC assay. It was found that four moles of Ce^{IV} required for oxidation of one mole TL based on which the stoichiometric equation may be shown as :

In a typical experiment tetralin (10 ml) was dissolved in (50 ml) acetonitrile-water mixture (60 : 40 v/v) which was treated with ceric ammonium nitrate (1 molar equivalent) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 60 min. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The solution was poured into water and the products were extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was chromatographed on silica gel column. The product (tetralone) was eluted with an increasing gradient of ethyl acetate in petroleum ether. The product was characterized as tetralone based on $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.09 (m, 3- CH_2), 2.55 (t, 4- CH_2), 2.87 (t, 2- CH_2), 7.19 (d, 5- CH), 7.21 (m, 7- CH), 7.38 (m, 6- CH), 7.93 (d, 8- CH).

Procedure and kinetic measurements :

All the chemicals were of highest purity and used without further purification. Doubly distilled water was used throughout. Ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) stock solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_6$ in 1 mol dm^{-3} of HNO_3 . The solution was standardized and stored in a dark coloured bottle and checked before each run. Tetraline stock solutions were prepared in water-acetonitrile mixture (60 : 40 v/v). Kinetic reactions were monitored on a 117 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Systronics) at 350 nm under pseudo-first order conditions and under inert atmosphere. H^+ ion concentration and ionic strength were maintained with required amounts of HNO_3 and KNO_3 solutions respectively. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) were computed by graphical methods and the experimental values were reproducible within $\pm 0.25\%$. Methods of computation of the order, rate constants and other kinetic parameters were the same as reported in our earlier studies³.

Conclusion :

An examination of rate constants and order of the reacting species, it reveals that partial oxidation takes place at aliphatic side chain in benzylic position. From this study it was found that ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)

in aqueous nitric acid medium selectively attack at benzylic position and generate free radicals, owing to their stability. Under the reaction conditions the process of oxidation is an excellent one to produce good yield of the product.

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